

README – Manuscript MS20180427

Overview

The code in this replication package constructs the analysis files and all results provided in the replication package using Stata. The main file runs all of the code to generate the data for the figures and tables in the paper. The replicator should expect the code to run for about 7-8 hours. The analysis relies on confidential data with restricted access. Access must be applied for through “The Institute of Evaluation of Labour Market and Education Policy (IFAU)” as described below. If data access is granted for replication, all results can be generated directly from the raw-data files in the data delivery.

Data Availability and Provenance Statements

Statement about Rights

- I certify that the author(s) of the manuscript have legitimate access to and permission to use the data used in this manuscript.

Summary of Availability

- **No data can be made** publicly available.

Data Sources

Public use data sourced from elsewhere

Data on Swedish national unemployment rates for different age groups from the Labor Force Survey of Statistics Sweden (2022a). The most recent numbers are available at: <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/labour-market/labour-force-surveys/labour-force-surveys-lfs/>. Note that time series is updated and not all years might be available online. A copy of the data is provided as part of this archive; Datafile: LFS_Unemployment.dta.

A data set that adjusts for changes in the categorization of Statistic Swedens (2022b) education classification variable over time. The key can be downloaded as an excel file (See heading “Nycklar mellan SUN-versioner, file SUN 69 (Old) – SUN 2000) via: <https://www.scb.se/dokumentation/klassifikation-och-standarder/svensk-utbildningsnomenklatur-sun>. Column A shows the old classification (SUN 69) and can be translated into the new

classification (SUN 2000) via columns C and D. The columns for translation are provided as part of this archive in .dta format; Datafile: translate_sun.dta.

Data on average wages of janitors (until 1996) and the 10th percentile of the Swedish wage distribution (from 1997) as a proxy for minimum wages (Sweden does not have a legislated minimum wage). The data is compiled based on wage data from Statistics Sweden. A copy of the data is provided as part of this archive; Datafile: minwage.dta.

Confidential Statistics Sweden data

All the results in the paper use confidential microdata from Statistics Sweden that have been accessed via the governmental agency "Institute of Evaluation of Labour Market and Education Policy (IFAU)". To gain access to the microdata for replication purposes (within the European Union), contact the IFAU record manager: <https://www.ifau.se/en/About-IFAU/Personnel/Administration/Anahid-Zakinian/> and request access to the data in project dnr 2015/3, folder YouthUnempl/EJ (IFAU, 2015). A detailed variable description is accessible via IFAU if access is granted. The following datasets are needed for replication and should be granted access to as part of project dnr 2015/3:

1. Yearly matched employer-employee registers (ANST), for years 1985-2010. Variables needed: persid (personal identifier), peorgnr (company id), cfarnr (establishment id), yrkstall (occupation codes), manfran (first month of employment), mantill (last months of employment), lonfink (labor income).
2. Yearly register over high school graduates (GYMA as combined file for years 1985-1989; GYMAVG for years 1986-2001 and GYMAE for years 2002-2010.) Variables needed: persid (personal id), avgygar (graduation year), gajmftal for years 1997-2001/Mbetygm for years 1990-1996/Gambet for years 1985-1989 (grade, variable name differs between years), Gaskkod (school id).
3. Register on multiple generations to match children and biological parents (FLERGEN09b). Variables needed: Persid (personal id), moder_persid (mother id), fader_persid (father id), moder_flandgrp (mother country of origin), fader_flandgrp (father country of origin).
4. Yearly registers on companies and their establishments including information on location and industry (FTGAST) for years 1985-2010. Variables needed: peorgnr (company id), cfarnr (plant id), astkom and astkom2 (municipality of establishment), Astsni (industry of establishment), instkod (institutional code), AFTgsni (industry of firm).

- Yearly registers on demographic characteristics of Sweden's entire population (LOUISESYS) for years 1985-2010. Variables needed: Persid (personal id), Civil (civil status), Kon (gender), Fodar (birth year), Fland (origin country), Invar (immigration year), Forsamli (municipality), Hsun/hsun2i/hsun2n (education level and field), Havar (last graduation year), Syss (employment status in November), Yrkstallnmod (occupation in November), Loneink (labor income), Studmed (study grants/benefits).

Dataset list

If access is granted, replication can be conducted directly the raw data files specified in the previous section. The code then generates the following data sets that are used for analysis.

Data file	Source	Notes	Provided
raw/LFS_unemployment.dta	Labor Force Survey		Yes
raw/minwage.dta			Yes
raw/translate_sun.dta	Statistics Sweden		Yes
use/FinalPanel.dta	Derived		No
use/descriptives_panelAB.dta	Derived		No
Use/86-10_descriptive.dta	Derived		No
Use/panelD.dta	Derived		No
use/Analyze_summerjob_YEAR.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR_plm_base.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR_plm.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapse_YEAR_p11_base.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapse_YEAR_p11.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR_leftiFE.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapse_YEAR_placebo_	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No

multi_iFE.dta			
use/Analyze_Matches_collapse_YEAR_small120.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapse_YEAR_small150.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapse_YEAR_empty1.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR_parent.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR_ac.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/Analyze_Matches_collapsed_YEAR_nj.dta	Derived	One file per year 1985-2010	No
use/KS_86-10.dta	Derived		No
use/estimates_main.dta	Derived		No
Use/estimates_main_ac.dta	Derived		No
use/estimates_main_nj.dta	Derived		No
Use/estimates_main_noparents.dta	Derived		No
Use/estimates_main_pl_iFE.dta	Derived		No
Use/estimates_main_left_iFE.dta	Derived		No
Use/estimates_wo.dta	Derived		No
Use/estimates_earn_ti_2020.dta	Derived		No

Computational requirements

Software Requirements

The replication package requires the use of Stata (code was last run with version 17.0, set version to 16.1)

- Requires installation of package `estout`
- The program “01_master_file.do” will install all dependencies and set up the environment, and should be run once.

Controlled Randomness

- Random seed is set at line 269 of program 02_graduate_panel and line 7 of program 04_contacts_panel_86-10_rep.do and line 10-11 of program T8_FGLS_rep.do.

Memory and Runtime Requirements

Summary

Approximate time needed to reproduce the analyses on a standard (2022) desktop machine:

- 7-8 hours

Details

The code was last run on a **Windows server 2019 standard with 512 GB of RAM, 54,5 TB of fast local storage.**

Description of programs/code

- The file `01_master_file.do` will call all the referenced data sets above and clean and prepare the data for analysis (files with prefixes 02 – 16).
- The master file will run all programs that generate all tables and figures in the main body and the appendices of the article. Each program called from `main.do` identifies the table or figure it creates. Output files are called appropriate names (`T3.tex`, `F1.png`) and should be easy to correlate with the manuscript.
- The programs listed in the section “controlled randomness” above include a random seed. If running in any order other than the one outlined below, your results may differ.

Instructions to Replicators

- Choose a default path for the replication files. The folder structure should look as described below and be saved in the default path that is chosen by you. Download the provided data sets “LFS_unemployment”, “translate_sun.dta” and “minwage.dta” and save them in the folder “default path\raw”. Confidential data should be stored in folder “default path\data”. All do-files should be saved in the folder “default path\do”.
If access is granted for replicating the data remotely, access should be directly granted to the folder “P:\2015\3\YouthUnempl\EJ”, which contains all folders, do-files and data needed for replication.
- Go to “default path\do” and open the do-file “01_master_file.do”. Edit `01_master_file.do` to adjust the default path to the main directory (if needed). If the data delivery is not already provided in the appropriate folder, save the confidential data files in “default path\data” or set a new path to the data delivery (NOT the same path as default path!) in line 30 of “01_master_file.do”.

- Run `programs/01_master_file.do` once on a new system to set up the working environment and run all steps in sequence. No further action is needed on the replicator's part.
- All tables are saved in folder "default path\output" and all figures are saved in folder "default path\output\graphs".

Details

- `programs/01_master_file.do`: will create all paths to the output directories, install needed ado packages.
 - These programs were last run at various times in 2022.
 - Order does matter. If run in a different order, results may differ.
 - `01_master_file.do` will run them all in sequence, which should take about 7 hours.
1. Programs for data cleaning and preparation of analysis data:
 The following programs create the sample of graduates for the descriptives and main analysis data set:
`02_graduate_panel_86-10_replicate.do`: creates sample of all graduates for descriptives
`03_summerjob_panel_86-10_rep.do`: creates data for descriptive analysis in T2, F2 and F3
`04_contacts_panel_86-10_rep.do`: creates main analysis data and left panel of Figures 4 and 5
 2. Placebos, robustness and additional analysis: Data cleaning and construction of additional analysis data sets
`05_cr_placebo_multi_rep.do`: creates data for placebo type 1 analysis and produces left panels of Figure 6
`06_cr_placebos_left_rep.do`: : creates data for placebo type 2 analysis and produces left panels of Figure 7
`07_generate_placebo_multi_iFE_rep.do`: creates data for using placebo type 1 as counterfactual and produces left panels of Figure A.1
`08_generate_placebo_left_iFE_rep.do`: creates data for placebo type 2 as counterfactual and produces left panels of Figure A.2
`09_graduate_panel_86-10_empt+1_rep.do` and `10_contacts_panel_empt+1_rep.do`: create sample and analysis data for column (5) of Table 4.
`11_contacts_panel_nojob_rep.do`: creates analysis data in Figures 8 and 9 and the left panel of Figure 9
`12_contacts_panel_wo_summerjob_rep.do`: creates analysis data for Figure A.3
`13_contacts_panel_exclparents_rep.do`: creates analysis data for Table A.2
`14_contacts_panel_academic_rep.do`: creates analysis data for Figure A.4
`15_contacts_panel_plantsize_rep.do`: creates analysis data for heterogeneity analysis in Table 6.

16_generate_KS_rep.do: creates analysis data set for Tables 7 and A.3

3. The following do-files produce the tables and figures in the main paper and appendix. See the list of tables and programs below for a detailed mapping:

F1_rep.do

T1_T3_descriptives.rep.do

T2_F2_F3_FGLS_rep.do

T4_F4b_F5b_FA5_FA6_FGLS_rep.do

T5_FA11_FA12_FGLS_rep.do

T6_FGLS_rep.do

T7_KS_do_rep.do

T8_FGLS_rep.do

F6_F7_FGLS_rep.do

F8_FGLS_rep.do

F9_FGLS_rep.do

FA1_FA2_FGLS_rep.do

FA3_FGLS_rep.do

FA4_FGLS_rep.do

TA2_FGLS_rep.do

FB1_FB2_FB3_rep.do

Please note that all do-files with the suffix “_FGLS” implement code adapted from Jaime-Castillo (2015) for re-weighting by the first-stage variance.

List of tables and programs

The provided code reproduces all tables and figures in the paper:

- Note that all subfigures for figures with several panels are provided separately and are not combined in one figure, i.e. Figure 2 which consists of four panels is provided as four separate figures, denoted F2a, F2b, F2c, F2d etc.
- Note that the code generates a separate table for each panel of a table. For instance, Table 1 consists of two panels A and B and the code generates tables T1_panelA and T1_panelB separately.

Figure/Table #	Program	Line Number	Output file
Figure 1	F1_rep.do		F1.png/.pdf
Figure 2	T2_F2_F3_FGLS_rep.do		F2a.pdf/png, F2b.pdf/png F2c.pdf/png, F2d.pdf/png
Figure 3	T2_F2_F3_FGLS_rep.do		F3a.pdf/png, F3b.pdf/png F3c.pdf/png, F3d.pdf/png
Figure 4	04_contacts_panel_86-10_rep.do (left panel) T4_F4b_F5b_FA6_FA6_FGLS_rep.do (right panel)	325-375	F4a.png/pdf F4b.pdf/png
Figure 5	04_contacts_panel_86-10_rep.do (left panel) T4_F4b_F5b_FA6_FA6_FGLS_rep.do (right panel)	379-426	F5a.png/pdf F5b.pdf/png
Figure 6	05_cr_placebos_multi_rep.do F6_F7_FGLS_rep.do	361-403, 576-619	F6a.pdf/png, F6c.pdf/png, F6b.pdf/png, F6d.pdf/png
Figure 7	06_cr_placebos_left_rep.do F6_F7_FGLS_rep.do	285-329, 626-669	F7a.pdf/png, F7c.pdf/png, F7b.pdf/png, F7d.pdf/png
Figure 8	F8_FGLS_rep.do		F8a.pdf/png, F8b.pdf/png, F8c.pdf/png, F8d.pdf/png
Figure 9	F9_FGLS_rep.do		F9b.pdf/png, F9d.pdf/png
Table 1	T1_T3_descriptives_rep.do	468-498	T1_panelA.doc/tex, T1_panelB.doc/tex
Table 2	T2_F2_F3_FGLS_rep.do		FGLS_T2_return.doc/tex

Table 3	T1_T3_descriptives_rep.do	499-563	FGLS_T2_moved.doc/tex T3_panelA.doc/tex, T3_panelB1.doc/tex, T3_panelB2.doc/tex, T3_panelD.doc/tex
Table 4	T4_F4b_F5b_FA6_FA6_FGLS_rep.do		FGLS_T4_return.doc/tex FGLS_T4_moved.doc/tex
Table 5	T5_FA11_FA12_FGLS_rep.do		FGLS_T5_return.doc/tex FGLS_T5_moved.doc/tex
Table 6	T6_FGLS_rep.do		FGLS_T6_return.doc/tex FGLS_T6_moved.doc/tex
Table 7	T7_FGLS_rep.do		T7_KSOutput.doc/tex (columns 2-6, column 1 from Table 4, column 2)
Table 8	T8_FGLS_rep.do	938-1005	FGLS_T8_MQ_c2.tex/doc (return links), FGLS_T8_MQ_c1.tex/doc (moved links)
Figure A.1	07_generate_placebo_multi_iFE.do FA1_FA2_FGLS_rep.do (right panel)	87-129	FA1a.pdf/png FA1b.pdf/png
Figure A.2	08_generate_placebo_left_iFE.do FA1_FA2_FGLS_rep.do (right panel)	30-72	FA2a.pdf/png FA2b.pdf/png
Figure A.3	FA3_FGLS_rep.do		FA3a.pdf/png, FA3b.pdf/png
Figure A.4	FA4_FGLS_rep.do		FA4a.pdf/png, FA4b.pdf/png
Figure A.5	T4_F4b_F5b_FA6_FA6_FGLS_rep.do		FA5a.png/pdf, FA5b.png/pdf
Figure A.6	T4_F4b_F5b_FA6_FA6_FGLS_rep.do		FA6a.pdf/png, FA6b.pdf/png
Figure A.7	T6_FGLS_rep.do		FA7a.pdf/png, FA7b.pdf/png
Figure A.8	T6_FGLS_rep.do		FA8a.pdf/png, FA8b.pdf/png
Figure A.9	T6_FGLS_rep.do		FA9a.pdf/png, FA9b.pdf/png

Figure A.10	T6_FGLS_rep.do	FA10a pdf/png, FA10b.pdf/png
Figure A.11	T5_FA11_FA12_FGLS_rep.do	FA11_FGLS_return_`j'.pdf/png for setors j=5,10,4,1,9,3
Figure A.12	T5_FA11_FA12_FGLS_rep.do	FA12_FGLS_moved_`j'.pdf/png for setors j=5,10,4,1,9,3
Table A.1	F6_F7_FGLS_rep.do	FGLS_TA1_multi.tex/doc, FGLS_TA1_left.tex/doc
Table A.2	TA2_FGLS_rep.do	FGLS_TA2_return.tex/doc, FGLS_TA2_moved.tex/doc
Table A.3	T7_KS_do_rep.do	TA3_KSOutputLocal.tex/doc (columns 2 & 3, column 1 from Table 7, column 5)
Figure B.1	FB1_FB2_FB3_rep.do	FB1a.pdf/png, FB1b.pdf/png
Figure B.2	FB1_FB2_FB3_rep.do	FB2a.pdf/png, FB2b.pdf/png
Figure B.3	FB1_FB2_FB3_rep.do	FB3a.pdf/png, FB3b.pdf/png

References

IFAU (2015). 'IFAU-databasen', Institute of Evaluation of Labour Market and Education Policy (IFAU), Uppsala Sweden.

Jaime-Castillo, A.M. (2015). 'Modeling multilevel data. the estimated dependent variable approach', https://www.stata.com/meeting/spain15/abstracts/materials/spain15_jaime.pdf, paper presented at the Spanish Stata Users Meeting, IE Business School (Madrid).

Statistics Sweden (2022a). 'Labour Force Surveys', <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/labour-market/labour-force-surveys/labour-force-surveys-lfs/>, (last accessed: 2022-03-10).

Statistics Sweden (2022b). 'Svensk utbildningsnomenklatur', <https://www.scb.se/dokumentation/klassifikationer-och-standarder/svensk-utbildningsnomenklatur-sun>, (last accessed: 2022-03-10).